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PHRASEOLOGISMS WITH ANTONYMOUS COMPONENT AND ISSUES OF THEIR ANALYSIS ACCORDING TO THEIR LEXICAL-SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS

Abstract.

Different methods can be used to reveal the lexical-semantic character of phraseologisms with an antonymic component: a complete sampling method, a classification method, as well as an analysis of the literature on the research problem. The uniqueness of these phraseological units lies in the difference of their lexemes and phrases. Phraseologisms are characterized by stability: reproduction in a finished form, semantic complexity, stability of lexical composition, morphological and syntactic fixation, non-modeling with a changing scheme of word combinations. According to A. Gurbanov, one of the components in the phraseological combination is necessarily used in its true meaning [Gurbanov 1989, p.227]. M.Mirzaliyeva places the combinations in the position between confluence and unity. According to his opinion, the combinations are close to the junctions based on the degree of integrity, to the junctions related to the changes occurring in the components [Mirzaliyeva 2009, p.97]. In our opinion, M. Mirzaliyeva's reference to the grammatical change of components goes beyond the limits of semantic connection.

Keywords: *Phraseologisms with antonym component, lexical-semantic feature, classification, method, analysis, antonymy.*

Introduction: Phraseological antonyms can partially overlap or completely differ due to their lexical composition. Each of these cases can be studied in different directions according to the lexical composition of phraseological antonyms. In order to study their lexical-semantic features, it is more appropriate to first examine those that partially overlap according to the lexical composition. All such issues are extensively analyzed in the article.

In phraseologisms with an antonym component, antonymy is revealed on the basis of different lexemes in the composition. For example: with a heavy heart – with a light heart; low tea – high tea; fair play – foul play; good form – bad form; in good faith – in bad faith; to be in smb.'s good books – to be in smb.'s bad book; a heart of gold – a heart of stone; to play one's cards well – to play one's cards badly, etc.

If we compare the pairs of antonyms in the given examples, we will find the differences heavy-light, low-high, fair-foul, good-bad, gold-stone, well-badly. The difference also attracts attention with the antonymy of lexical units. Among the examples, there are many that are fixed with the participation of bad-good elements.

During the study of the lexical semantic features of phraseology, it is necessary to differentiate between the lexical meaning of the word and the meaning of the phraseology. Because the meaning of phraseologism is more complex.

It is known that the meaning of phraseologism "expresses information that cannot be fixed by the corresponding free combination model that is semantically complex" [Kunin p.140]. Nevertheless, lexical units and phraseology are not isolated from each other in the language system, they act as closely related units. Phraseologisms are formed on the basis of semantic-grammatical features, their constituent elements are selected by internal connection.

It is possible to identify the substantive phraseologisms of the English language with lexemes due to their general categorical meaning. Substantive phraseologisms, like nouns, have an object-categorical meaning. Nevertheless, significant differences in the meaning of the word with substantive phraseology are revealed. In English, there are three types of relationship between a substantive phraseology and a word: 1) the meaning of substantive phraseology with an adjective component coincides with the meaning of the word; bad blood – enmity; Chinese whispers – gossip, etc. It should be noted that such similarity is conditional. Categorical specificity and limitation in replacing words with phraseologisms in different contexts do not give reason to talk about identity; 2) the meaning of the majority of substantive phraseology containing adjectives cannot be given in one word. This aspect shows that phraseologism has a large semantic volume. For example, a free agent – an independent person, a person who is independent in his actions; a live wire – an active person; reliable person; cheerful person etc.; 3) most nouns in the language have no phraseological equivalent. This is also natural. Because the phraseological unit fulfills the nominative function and gives a certain characteristic of the subject. The individuality in the meaning of the phraseological unit manifests itself in expressing the individual signs as well as the general signs of a certain subject [Shubarchik 2003, p. 7].

The semantic organization of the phraseological system of the language is one of the most important issues in linguistics. Many studies have been conducted in this area [See: Akhmanova, Vasil'eva, Alufirenko, Melerovich, etc.].

Semantic theory shows that phraseological meaning is a multi-level complex system. N.F. Alefirenko shows that any structure is a set of regular connections and relationships of the elements that make up this system [Alefirenko, 1998, p.5]. The nature of the structure is determined by the relationship and effects between

the elements. In order to understand the semantic structure of phraseologisms, first of all, it is necessary to know the semantic structure of lexemes. L.M. Vasiliev analyzed the meaning structure of words and distinguished sems as elementary constituents of their meaning [Vasiliev L., 1990, p. 37].

Analysis: Phraseological meaning has denotative-significant and connotative aspects. In other words, the meaning consists of denotative, significant and connotative terms. These three types of sem are separated from the lexical meaning of the word.

On the basis of denotation, which is the subject of the objective world, in phraseologism, the concept of meaning - object is formed. The meaning structure of phraseologism includes more sem or semantic component.

Semes in phraseologism are divided into main (categorical, archisem) and dependent or subcategorical semesters. A subcategorical clause is a clarifying, complementary clause. Besides, in the structure of phraseological meaning there are also integral, common for similar units of this class, differential, utilitarian and occasional, actualized and non-actualized, real and potential semes that distinguish the units of one class [Melchul, 1999, p. 124]. Complexity in the meaning of phraseologism comes from the presence of various generalizing (group, subcategorical, categorical) terms [Chepasova 2006, p.30].

In English, the denotation of the phraseological unit *bad actor* is a bad actor. This actor cannot please the audience, he plays his role badly. The meaning of the phraseological unit means "dangerous, bad person". Categorical sem is the subject. Subcategorical sem person, group meaning sem is revealed as "bad character person". The antonym of a phraseological unit is not formed by replacing the word "bad" with "good". "Good actor" is a free phrase.

V. D. Margulis, who studied the meaning of phraseologisms of the English language, gave a new description of the phraseological meaning. He distinguished the main figurative meaning (meaning-image) and the genetic meaning or prototype (meaning-prot-image) in phraseological units. According to his opinion, image - meaning creates a figural complex. This complex consists of intensional and implicational, which make up the core. The intentional meaning of the image expresses the content of the concept and includes a set of semantic signs. Their presence is mandatory for the denotations of the given class. A strong implication incorporates features that may not be involved in meaning.

Big dog noun phraseology in English is big man, important man, etc. has meanings. The intensional of the image-meaning includes the words "angry, serious man", the strong implicational meaning "demanding", the weak implicational "non-treacherous", and the negative implicational "benevolent" and "friendly" terms. Proobraz's intensional means "big, scary dog".

According to N.F. Alefirenko, the main aspect of phraseological meaning has a complex structural structure, it is defined by the intensional or conceptual core and the implicational-peripheral meaning. It is characterized by the hierarchical dependence of intensional

archisems and differential sems. Implicational intensional is conditioned by phraseological meaning and is divided into two structurally organized zones. The first of these is the perinuclear zone and forms potential sems. The periphery is characterized by hidden sems. The core of phraseological meaning includes extralinguistic and linguistic denotations. These denotations create an association with the images and objects of real reality. Connotative terms are located in the periphery, the expressed subject forms a new view [Alefirenko, 2000, p. 74].

In the phraseological sense, the main connotative component is included in the subject - logical content. This component expresses the attitude of the speaker to the named object. The connotative component is very complex in its structure. Therefore, it is difficult to accurately translate this component.

A.V. Kunin connotative meaning of phraseology includes stylistic shades and emotional-expressive aspect [Kunin 2005, p.86].

The evaluative component of the connotative sem includes the opinion of the "evaluator subject about the positive and negative aspects of what is expressed." For example, a bad, good offices, poor taste, etc.

The emotive component of the connotative sem in of phraseologism is related to the evaluative component. This component expresses the speaker's feelings towards the subject and conveys various emotions. Phraseology can also express a feeling other than a single evaluation [Shubarchik 2003, p. 64].

The expressive component of the connotative sem is closely related to the imagery of phraseologism. Figurative expressiveness is based on metaphorical transfer. The best card - solid evidence.

Revealing the stylistic component of the connotative element of the meaning of phraseologism allows to attribute phraseological units to a certain style. For example, eternal triangle, favorable cards, iron nerves, an open question, etc.

Thus, the general meaning of phraseologism includes the meanings of connotative and denotative-significant terms. The denotative-significant aspect is distinguished by subject orientation. The connotative meaning of phraseologism is expressed by additional communicatively important social and individual features.

Phraseological unit, in addition to naming the subject, sign and event, gives its characteristics, evaluates it, etc. A set of semantic and structural signs is characteristic for phraseologism. Each phraseological unit has a component composition, and the specific functions of these components are manifested in the composition of the phraseological unit. According to V. P. Zhukov, the component of the phraseological unit is under the influence of phraseological and lexical-semantic forces. From the semantic point of view, highly loaded components form an integral part of the phraseological structure [Zhukov 2006, p. 14]. From the mentioned aspect, the problem of the essence of the component composition of phraseological antonyms is of special interest. The fact that the components of antonymous phraseology themselves form an antonymous pair also plays a special role here.

Contrast in phraseological antonyms is often based on lexical antonymy. The antonymy of lexical units denoting sign, movement, direction of blessing, quality, as well as evaluation also conditions the antonymy of phraseological units. First of all, it is justified to conduct a lexical-semantic analysis based on such components of antonym phraseology.

In the antonym pair with a heavy heart-with a light heart, three components coincide, one component is different: heavy - light. These two components form an antonymous pair. Phraseological combinations that include them are also antonymous phraseologisms.

The phraseological unit "With a heavy heart" means "with concern".

My fellow Americans and friends in foreign lands, I speak to you this morning with a heavy heart [with a heavy heart//context.reverso.net/перевод/].

With a light heart - "with ease", "with joy", "with sincerity" of that is, we know how to laugh, but with a light heart, we can laugh, but laughing with a pure heart does not always turn out right [with a light heart // context.reverso.net/ перевод/].

In English, the words "flimsy", "light", "mild", "weak" are mentioned as antonyms of the word "heavy". However, it is possible to correct the antonym of the phraseological unit "with a heavy heart" only by using the word "light".

The combination of the word heart with the words "heavy" and "light" in the compared and contrasted antonym pair realizes the emergence of basic semantics. In the literal translation, the word combinations "heavy heart" and "light heart" are obtained, the use of the word "with" and the indefinite article in a phraseological combination creates the equivalents "with a heavy heart" and "with a light heart". In the Azerbaijani language, as well as in the English language, no new meaning is formed from this combination, based on the summation of the meanings of the components. The combination does not carry information about the heaviness or lightness of the heart. Here the evaluation of the feeling held or experienced takes place. As a result, these meanings are formed in the phraseology containing the combination "heavy heart". The pair of heavy-light antonyms are gradual antonyms. There is no sharp pairing of antonyms in this pair. Because neither the maximum limit of weight nor lightness is known. The gradation is arranged as the lightness goes from the minority degree to the majority degree. For example, very light → a little light → light. It is possible to grade the word heavy in the same way: a little heavy → a little heavy → heavy → very heavy, etc.

With a bad grace – with a good grace phraseological pair of antonyms is formed on the basis of the previous structure. Here, the words that differ from the components form a lexical antonym pair: bad-good. Of course, ranking is conditional. That is, it is possible to show the pair of antonyms in the form of good-bad.

After last night, he's in the king's good grace.

All good grace with me was lost the moment you signed up with our wretched siblings [with good grace // context. reverso.net/перевод/].

Depending on the context, the semantics of the

combination "good grace" can change. This feature affects the phraseological unit "with good grace". Let's try to explain on the basis of these few examples.

(1) Please play game with good grace.

(2) If he says what he's going to do on time, with good grace and a fine price.

(3) Accept this victory with good grace [with good grace // context.reverso.net].

Result: Thus, as it is clear from the examples, in the first of the three given examples, the phraseological unit was translated as "with heart", in the second as "honestly", and in the third as "correct". Therefore, the semantics of a phraseological unit depends on the context in which it is used. At the same time, this dependence has a dependence on the meanings of the components or lexemes that make up the phraseological unit. In the phraseology "with good grace" used in the examples, the supporting word is the lexeme "grace". The adjective "Good" adds a positive tone to it. In the phraseology formed according to the same structure and in which the adjective "good" is replaced by "bad", "bad" adds a negative tone to the meaning. Let's consider the processing of the antonym phraseology, that is, the phraseological unit "with bad grace" in a sentence.

"But I got a bad vibe about Grace Cochran" - But I got a bad vibe about Grace Cochran.

No, I'm sticking with bad grace – I insist - it's a bad idea. [context.reverso.net /перевод/ английский-русский, with-bad-grace].

Apparently, in these examples, the lexeme "bad" has a negative connotation in the semantics.

Most of the phraseologisms contain a certain image at the stage of formation, which becomes the organizer of its meaning. In other words, the image of a phraseology is an important component of the meaning of a phraseology, a figurative internal form. Without an image and, therefore, without an internal form, phraseologism has neither meaning nor itself. Therefore, a phraseological unit that has lost its internal form cannot perform any communicative function. This follows from the fact that there is a close connection between the internal form, meaning and functionality of phraseologism. This is such a relationship that one form does not exist without the other" [А. Баранов. 2009. p. 23].

Contrastive or contradictory imagery is formed by antonymous lexemes in phraseological units (for example, top-bottom, bad-good, dark-light, heavy-light, etc.). Such lexemes reveal contrast vectors of antonymous phraseology: to come out on top – to be on top. Metaphorical imagery in the meaning of phraseological units is based on the association reflecting the similarity between heterogeneous essences, and in this case the conceptual metaphor is abstracted at different levels, emerges in one of the types of invariant scheme or invariant image [Stebelkova 2009, p.75]. It is clear that the semantic process is based on the cognitive process. The figurative structure of a phraseological unit is a multi-level structure. These levels are as follows: 1) cognitive level; 2) semantic level; 3) verbal level. If the cognitive level is represented by conceptual schemes, the semantic level is represented by images taken from certain fields of understanding. The verbal level is pro-

vided by means of language that express individual images. In the cognitive analysis, the process of formation of antonymic meanings is investigated, while the correlation at the cognitive and semantic sub-levels is in the center of attention.

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